

Employing Cutting-Edge Methodologies for In-Depth Spatiotemporal Analysis of Water Quality Dynamics in Serbian Rivers

Maja Brborić, Sonja Dmitrašinović, Sanja Čojbašić, Maja Turk Sekulić, **Jelena Radonić**

Department of Environmental Engineering and Occupational Safety and Health, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 6, 21 000 Novi Sad, Serbia

E-mail of the presenting author: jelenaradonic@uns.ac.rs.

Introduction

The Danube River in Serbia is confronting significant pollution challenges, particularly near major urban and industrial centers such as Belgrade and Novi Sad. Current monitoring systems provide insufficient insight into the temporal and spatial fluctuations in water quality. This study, covering the period from 2011 up to 2022, aims to identify pollution hotspots and elucidate the factors influencing water quality. Data from 12 localities along the Danube and Tisza Rivers were analysed using hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) to uncover pollution patterns across 19 physical and chemical parameters.

Key findings indicate that Bezdán, Novi Sad, and Bogojevo on the Danube consistently exhibited elevated contamination levels, while Novi Bečej and Titel on the Tisza were also notably affected. An expanded dataset incorporating six additional localities identified Zemun and Novi Sad additionally, as the major pollution hotspots. The analysis revealed untreated municipal and industrial wastewater as primary pollution sources, highlighting the need for targeted remediation efforts.

The study further examined the impacts of seasonal, meteorological, and anthropogenic factors on water quality. Variations in industrial discharges, agricultural runoff, and weather patterns were found to significantly influence fluctuations in water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and nutrient levels. To improve measurement accuracy, a novel mobile sensor system was deployed along the Danube and Sava rivers, capturing over 7,700 real-time data points for key parameters. This system, which included measurements in segments such as Marina Dorćol and Marina Zemun, demonstrated significant oscillations in conductivity, driven by both, natural cycles and pollution sources.

Comparative analysis with stationary SEPA data [1] underscored discrepancies, illustrating the enhanced effectiveness of mobile monitoring in capturing spatial and temporal dynamics of water quality. Specifically, our measurements were compared with data from SEPA's Zemun station, revealing that, while SEPA classified the Danube as Class I water, our data suggested Class I based on conductivity, but Class V based on pH and oxygen levels. This classification indicates a poor ecological status, implying that the surface water is unsuitable for any use.

The observed variations may stem from several factors, including the upstream location of SEPA's Zemun station relative to our monitoring sites and the stationary nature of SEPA's measurements compared to our mobile, high-resolution data. This study emphasizes the necessity of implementing continuous, high-resolution monitoring systems to identify and mitigate pollution sources effectively. Such systems will facilitate a more precise understanding of water quality dynamics and support targeted environmental management strategies to safeguard the ecological health of the Danube River.

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Reference

[1] www.sepa.gov.rs (07/09/2024).